

SEED SELECTION TECHNOLOGY OF OIL CROP IN AGRICULTURE

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It is known that the fertility of the seeds of any agricultural crops in laboratory and field conditions, as well as the productivity as a result, are directly related to their quality indicators. Agricultural crop seed quality can be measured in a variety of ways, including cleaning and grading. However, until now there is no device for sorting or cleaning soybean seeds in the technological systems of seed preparation of agricultural production in our country [1, 2]. Therefore, since the quality indicators of soybean seeds being prepared for planting are low, they do not fully meet the agrotechnical requirements, the consumption of one hectare of land is 2-3 times more than the scientifically based standards, and 120 man·hours/ha of additional manual labor has to be used to collect the surplus seedlings. As a result, thousands of tons of seeds that can be used for human consumption and animal feed are thrown into the ground and wasted [3]. This leads to an excessive increase in the scale of expenses for the cultivation of oilseeds and an increase in the cost of the harvested product.

The principle of operation of all grain cleaning and sorting machines is based on the shape and size of the seeds, and they are divided into machines that sort grain using wind and sieves, and machines that sort grain and other seeds by length using trainers, sieves, wind and triers.

Machines that clean and sort grain from various impurities with the help of wind and wind are carried out in grain sorters. VS2, VS8, and VS10 grain sorting machines are used in practice. The principle of operation of these machines is the same, they differ from each other in terms of productivity, number of gears, structure and size of nodes. The grain mixture falls from the hopper through a window with a sliding cover to the first hopper at the top of

the machine. The air stream coming out of the fan blows out the light impurities in the grain falling into the hopper outside the machine. Large impurities (cobs, straw, cuttings, pieces of iron, stones) fall from the upper halvir through the tarvans to both sides of the manshna. The rest of the grain passes through the holes of the hopper and pours into the lower hoppers located next to each other. The whole grain remains on the surface of the grain and moves towards the second grain. The grain is separated into two types in this hopper: the second sort passes through the holes of the hopper and falls under the machine, and the first sort remains on the surface of the hopper and falls to the other side.

Sorting and cleaning in the above-mentioned devices is not economically efficient. This is due to the fact that, firstly, the price of these sorters is very expensive, secondly, their use in technological systems for preparing small seeds for planting or on farms is not economically justified due to their high productivity, and thirdly, the possibility of sorting small seeds according to all important physical and mechanical properties is limited in these devices. [4].

It is known from scientific sources that in order to obtain high-quality seeds with close biological properties, it is necessary to sort them according to all important physical and mechanical properties. This requirement is fully met by the sorting of agricultural crop seeds in the electric field. Because the electric field affects the seeds with an electric field force directed to them, taking into account all their important physical-mechanical properties, that is, the electric field affects the seeds with an electric force of different values, taking into account all their important physical-mechanical properties. As a result, the seeds are sorted in the electric field according to all important physico-mechanical properties, i.e. mass, geometric size, density, electrical properties [5, 6].

It should also be noted that the electric field has a positive effect on the germination of seeds in laboratory and field conditions and the growth of seedlings.

Taking this into account, we recommend using an electrotechnological device for sorting and cleaning soybean seeds. The advantage of the electrotechnological device over other filters is, firstly, its structure is simple, secondly, it is easy to prepare, thirdly, it is energy and resource efficient, fourthly, it is safe from electricity and fire, and fifthly, most importantly, it does not need an external source to generate a high voltage electric field [7].

In the proposed electrotechnological device, the electric field is generated as a result of the friction of two dielectric materials rotating against each other, that is, a dielectric drum and a separating brush [8]. The seeds falling on the

surface of the charged rotating dielectric drum are polarized and separated into the seed or technical fraction based on the mutual ratio of the acting forces. Taking into account the above, this project envisages the development of a pilot copy of an electrotechnological device for sorting and cleaning soybean seeds and testing the seeds prepared for sowing in laboratory and field conditions.

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